

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS.

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The inclusion of the textile and clothing industry in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the basic branches of processing is due to the country's long-term specialization in cotton, the availability of conditions for deep processing of raw materials, especially in creating new jobs. In this regard, the President and the Government of our country pay great attention to the development of this sector and increase its competitiveness. In particular, the program of measures for further development of the textile and garment industry for 2017-2019 was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2016 No PP-2687. This program is primarily aimed at solving the problems that have accumulated in the industry for many years, and includes measures aimed at the rapid development of the structure and infrastructure of the textile industry.

We would like to draw attention to one of the problems mentioned in our article, which is “...Stable dominance of production and export of semi-finished textile products, insufficient production of high value-added finished textile products and formation of national brands that can compete in world markets do not allow to increase the income of textile enterprises.⁵”

The systemic nature of this problem is not solved by correcting the activities of a single enterprise, but requires an innovative approach to the content of entrepreneurial activity in this area.

Complex competitiveness is a term that covers all aspects of the enterprise, which includes not only a competitive advantage in foreign markets, but also the competitiveness of the internal environment. If we take complex competitiveness as an integral indicator, it includes resource competitiveness, investment, innovation, technology, marketing and logistics, management competitiveness.

⁵ On measures to accelerate the development of the textile and clothing industry. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017 No. PF-5285. Electronic source. www.lex.uz.

Cluster theory has entered the scientific process in the form of a marketing strategy, as an idea-method that enables enterprises of the state, regions and regions to win in a competitive environment in the market.

Although the idea of increasing the competitiveness of national and regional economies based on the practical application of the cluster strategy has its own characteristics in different countries and industries, but M. Porter and M. Enright revealed that it has the following common priorities:

- Opportunities will be created for enterprises (firms) to increase labor productivity and production efficiency due to direct access to suppliers, qualified personnel, information, service and training centers. In enterprises of clustered regions, labor productivity is up to 1.5 times higher, and wages are up to 30 percent higher;

There will be conditions for educational and research centers to create new scientific and methodological developments, test them in the short term, introduce them into production;

There will be favorable conditions for further stimulation of the work of workers and specialists in production and research and the creation of new products.

In our opinion, the formation of clusters in the system of textile and light industry of Uzbekistan is appropriate if it is carried out not on a national scale, but on the basis of specific socio-economic conditions in the regions, based on the essence of cluster theory.

In our opinion, in the context of market relations, it is expedient to establish a department of marketing services in enterprises. The functions of this department are:

- a comprehensive analysis of the market conditions and scope of the enterprise's intended sales;

- study the needs, demands and purchasing power of potential consumers;

- planning of production and sale of goods;

- organization of marketing and sales of goods and sales promotion;

- price planning and advertising;

- organization, management and control of marketing activities in the company;

- development and implementation of the marketing strategy of the enterprise.

In addition, the marketing services department identifies the enterprise's production, resource, and export capabilities. To do this, it must perform the following analytical tasks:

- analysis of the financial and economic condition of the enterprise; product range inspection; assessment of the production capacity of the enterprise;

determine the strategy of the enterprise to enter foreign markets; creation of websites on the company's access to foreign markets.

It is recommended that the Marketing Services Department take into account the following in the implementation of product policy:

develop and implement measures to extend the life of goods as much as possible and for the required period, as well as the strategy of action specific to each stage;

implement an innovation policy and launch the production of new products;

pursuing an assortment policy aimed at identifying a group of goods that will ensure high profitability of the enterprise, allow it to take a strong position in the market.

The marketing services department should develop an export strategy for the enterprise. To do this, it should indicate the advantages and goals of exports, the priorities and methods of its implementation, as well as ways to provide resources and funds for their implementation.

In our opinion, in order to improve the conduct of marketing research in export-oriented enterprises, it is advisable to establish a department of marketing services in the organizational structure of management. This section should perform the following functions:

- Carrying out a systematic and comprehensive analysis of the state of the enterprise, identifying the causes of failure, the use of experience and achievements in marketing policy and marketing activities;

development of marketing strategy, definition of the main marketing goal, definition of directions of its improvement, adaptation of production to consumer demand, ie definition and formation of the purpose, strategy and tactics;

- organization of marketing activities, coordination of activities of various services and departments, implementation of conjuncture-debate work, study of the market and prospects of its development, study of the strategy of a competing firm;

- organization of advertising, selection of the most optimal options for advertising, the implementation of advertising text and artistic design;

- Organization and holding of exhibitions and fairs to familiarize consumers with goods and services

determine the time and place;

- Carrying out patent research, organization and participation in the creation of new products, improving product quality;

- organization of effective sales of goods and services, control of supply, optimization of stocks, implementation of efficient movement of goods;

- organization of constant marketing control, analysis of management decisions and their effectiveness, constant control of marketing expenses on advertising activity on the criterion of "cost - result";

- organization of accounting in marketing activities, determination and calculation of performance indicators, incentives for each marketing employee

In short, the success of export-oriented enterprises largely depends on the effective organization and improvement of marketing services in enterprises.

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